

Awareness Regarding First Aid Management of Sports Injury among Primary School Teacher

N. Sivasubramanian¹, Chaudhari Ankita², Patel Janu³, Baranda Prince⁴, Bhoi Aradhana⁵, Chaudhari Binal⁶,
Chaudhari Janvi⁷, Chaudhari Jay⁸

¹ Professor, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University Visnagar, Gujrat-384315

² Assistant Professor, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University Visnagar, Gujrat-384315

³ Nursing Tutor, Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University Visnagar, Gujrat-384315

⁴⁻⁸ Nootan College Of Nursing, Sankalchand Patel University

ABSTRACT: First aid management of sports injury means during the time of any sports activity injury occur in children that time what type of first aid management is given to resolve the wound or any injury and to prevent complication. So, that the basic knowledge of first aid is required in primary school teacher.

Objective: 1. to assess the knowledge regarding first aid management of sports injury among primary school teachers 2. To the effectiveness of health education regarding first aid management of sports injury among primary school teachers 3. To associate the knowledge with selected demographic variable.

Research approach: Quantitative research approach.

Research design: Experimental design

Participation: 40 primary school teacher.

Tool: Questionnaire was used to assess the level of knowledge among primary school teacher.

Results: The comparison of mean and standard deviation of pre - test and post - test level of knowledge regarding management of sports injury among primary school teacher. The mean score was increased from 10.55 to 16 which showed a marked deference of 5.45 respectively and the standard deviation was 0.300 to 0.42 after the administration of health education. 'T' test value is 11.94. This value is significant at $p < 0.05$ level. It indicate the effectiveness of health education on increasing the level of knowledge regarding first aid management of sports injury among primary school teacher. Hence the hypothesis was accepted.

Conclusion: Teachers had increase level of knowledge.

KEY WORDS: Assess, Effectiveness, Health education.

BACKGROUND

“If a child lives with approval he learns to like himself”- Joel hardy

First aid is the first and immediate assistance given to any person suffering from either a minor or serious illness or injury, with care provided to preserve life, prevent the condition from worsening, or to promote recovery. It includes initial intervention in a serious condition prior to professional medical help being available, such as performing cardiopulmonary resuscitation (CPR) while waiting for an ambulance, as well as the complete treatment of minor conditions, such as applying a plaster to a cut. First aid is generally performed by someone with basic medical training. Mental health first aid is an extension of the concept of first aid to cover mental health, while psychological first aid is used as early treatment of people who are at risk for developing PTSD. Conflict First Aid, focused on preservation and recovery of an individual's social or relationship wellbeing, is being piloted in Canada.

According to national first aid science advisory board, first aid should be learned by every person for this it is necessary that first aid training and education should be provided to everyone and should be important t. In childhood school life plays an important role for everyone. It has a great or direct impact on children's physical and mental development. As the children come under the vulnerable group they are more important to get injuries and accidents especially when they are in school going age because at that time they are still maturing physically and mentally. In school teachers are the first caregivers who protect the children from trauma and accidents. Every teacher should have the ability to deal with any health emergency condition, when a children need healthcare. The victim should get immediate management of any accidents or trauma for good and early prognosis

Accidents can happen anywhere at any time. The consequence of unintentional accident can be life threatening. Unintentional accident needs immediate and appropriate life saving care before the affected person get major treatment. This life saving care or first aid is an assessment and interventions that can be carried out by a person nearby immediately with minimal or without medical equipment. Therefore, this makes it important to have basic knowledge of first aid. The ultimate goal of first aid is to stop or to reverse the possible harm at a given time before reaching the appropriate health care center. First aid knowledge is methods and techniques that used perform practices related to prevention and immediate response to health emergencies. It can be given in all areas such as household, schools, workplace, and recreational areas. Beyond health matters, first aid knowledge also increases the social responsibility of the society and strengthens values.

It is very difficult for a man to go out somewhere and return safely because we cannot give any guarantee or security to our life. This is the world of accidental world. So many accidents occur in many places like in schools, during travelling, when doing our daily activities and place is left out. People motive is just to get away from the place when accident occurs. They do not come forward to help or to have some first aid care because they are not aware of giving first aid for injuries. We could see the same situations in the school also. A lot of care must be taken while the students are in the schools playground or in public places. So they must have awareness on first aid and that has to be given for the school teachers. Because, first aid training not only provide with knowledge and skills to give life but also help to develop safety awareness and habits that promote safety at home, at work, during recreation and on the streets and highways.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research approach adopted for present study evaluative approach. In the present study the investigator selected pre-experimental one group pretest post test design. The setting for this study as the selected primary school in mahesana districts. The sample selected for the present study comprised of primary school teacher in selected primary school in mahesana district. Sample size consists of 40 teachers in selected primary school teacher in mehsana district. A Non probability convenient sampling technique is used for this study.

RESULTS

Description of demographic variable of primary school teachers.

This section deals with the description of the demographic characteristics of the primary school teacher and has been presented in the form frequency and percentage.

Table 1: frequency and percentage distribution of primary school teacher according to characteristics.

Sr.No.	Demographic variable	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
1.	Age:-		
	20-25 years	01	2.5%
	26-35 years	05	12.5%
	36-45 years	34	85%
2.	Gender:-		
	Male	12	30%
	Female	28	70%
3.	Religion:-		
	Hindu	40	100%
	Islam	00	00%
	Christian	00	00%
	Other	00	00%

4.	Monthly income:- 20,000 – 30,000 31,000 – 40,000 41,000 – 50,000 51,000 & above	01 08 05 26	2.5% 20% 12.5% 65%
5.	Education qualification PTC B.ed B.Sc Other	21 08 02 09	52.5% 20% 05% 22.5%
6.	Previous knowledge Yes No	28 12	70% 30%

Age In Year: - Regarding Age, Categories Of The Respondents Has Been Divided Into Three Different

Categories. Among 2.5% Of Respondents Belongs To Age 20-25 Years, 12.5% Of Respondents Belongs To Age 26-35 Years, 85% Responders Belongs To Age 36-45 Years. Gender :- The Above Mentioned Table Deals With The Demographic Data Of Sample With Regard To Gender. Majority Of Sample Belong To The Female Category (70%) Whereas (30%) Belongs To The male Category. Religion:- All The Teacher Belong To Hindu Religion (100%). Monthly Income :- Regarding Monthly Income, Categories Of The Respondents Has Been Divided Into Four Categories. Among 2.5% Of Respondents Belong To 20,000-30,000 Income, 20% Of Respondents Belong To 31,000- 40,000 Income, 12.5% Respondents Belong To 41,000-50,000 Income, 65% Respondents Belong To 51,000 & Above Income. Education Qualification:- Regarding Education Qualification, Categories Of The respondents Has Been Divided Into Four Categories. Among 52.5% Of Respondents Belong To Ptc, 20% Of Respondents Belong To B.Ed, 5% Of Respondents Belong To B.Sc. And 22.5% Of Respondents Belong To Other. Previous Knowledge:- Regarding Previous Knowledge, Categories Of The Respondents Has-been Divided Into Two Categories. Among 70% Of Respondents Having Previous Knowledge And 30% Of Responder Having No Previous Knowledge.

Significant difference of knowledge score of first aid management of sports injury among the primary school teacher before and after health education:- part 1:- self structure question tool:-

Table 2:- frequency and percentage distribution of knowledge of primary school teacher.

N=40

Level of Knowledge	Pre - test		Post-test	
	F	%	F	%
Poor (1-7)	04	10%	00	00%
Average (8-14)	36	90%	09	22.5%
Good (15-20)	00	00%	31	77.5%

Data in table 2 show that prior to the administration of health education, 10% of sample had poor knowledge (score: 1-7) regarding first aid management of sports injury among the primary school teacher, while the average knowledge (score: 8-14) was observed in 90% of the sample. In the post-test there was marked improvement in the knowledge of sample with majority (77.5%) gained good knowledge (score: 15-20), (22.5%) gained average knowledge (score: 8-14).

Effectiveness of health education regarding first aid management of sports injury among the primary school teacher:-

To find the significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-test knowledge score, “t” test used. In order to test the statistical significance between the mean pre-test and post-test knowledge score. Mean, mean difference, Standard Deviation and “t” test value of level of knowledge regarding first aid management of sports injury among primary school teacher.

Table:- 3 Mean standard deviation and mean difference of pre-test and post-test knowledge score of primary school teacher. N=40

Parameter	Mean	Standard deviation	Mean Difference	T value
Pre-test	10.55	0.300	5.45	11.94
Post-test	16	0.42		

The data presented in Table 3 shows that the data also depicts that the mean post-test knowledge score (16 ± 0.42) was apparently higher than that of mean pre-test (10.55 ± 0.300) knowledge score. Hypothesis H1 was accepted hence it can be inferred that the health education was highly effective in increasing the knowledge of primary school teacher regarding first aid management of sports injury.

Fig -1 comparison of mean percentage of pre-test and post-test knowledge score.

Overall pre-test knowledge 52.75%. In the post-test overall knowledge is 80%. The mean difference percentage or the effectiveness of intervention knowledge is 27.3%.

Table 4:- association between level of knowledge regarding first aid management of sports injury among the primary school teacher with their selected demographic variable.

Demographic variables	F	poor	average	good	X ²	DF	“T” Value
N=40							
Age:-							
A. 20-25	01	00	01	00	0.71	02	5.99
B. 26-35	05	01	04	00			
C. 36-45	34	03	31	00			
Gender:-							
A. Male	12	02	10	00	0.84	01	3.84
B. female	28	02	26	00			
Religion:-							
A. Hindu	40	04	36	00	00	01	3.84
B. Islam	00	00	00	00			
C. Christian	00	00	00	00			
D. Other	00	00	00	00			
Monthly income:-							
A. 20,000 - 30,000	01	00	01	00	0.79	03	7.81
B. 31,000 – 40,000	08	01	07	00			
C. 41,000 – 50,000	04	00	05	00			
D. 51,000 & above	26	03	23	00			
Education Qualification.							
A. PTC	21	02	19	00	0.29	03	7.81
B. B.ed	08	01	07	00			
C. B.sc	02	00	02	00			
D. Other	08	01	08	00			
Previous knowledge							
A. Yes	28	03	25	00	0.53	01	3.84
B. No	12	01	11	00			

Table 4 shows that the association between the pre-test of knowledge and socio demographic variable. Based on the third objectives used to chi-square test to associate the level of knowledge and selected demographic variable. The chi-square value show that three significance between education status, health personnel and mass media with any previous knowledge demographic variable and pre-test knowledge score. The calculated chi-square value less than table value at 0.05 level of significance.

CONCLUSION

The finding of the study concluded that there was significant increase in the Level of knowledge and good expressed practice of primary school teachers. After Programmed teaching using video on first aid Management among primary school Teachers. The level knowledge increased and expressed practices Improved due to Effectiveness of Programmed teaching

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